

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF FIBER-REINFORCED CONCRETE

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SUMMARY: The present paper deals with the problem of modeling the complete macroscopic response of short fibre reinforced cementitious composites under unidirectional tensile loading. It is considered a concrete matrix with a periodic distribution of cracks and fibres. A cell model is used to represent the periodic microstructure and the overall properties of the composite are defined using the homogenization theory for material with periodic microstructure. The damage of the FRC is modeled considering the evolution of a process zone and a propagation of an initial crack, taking into account the bridging action of the fibers. A new numerical procedure is developed to evaluate the nonlinear response of the material. In particular, the softening process is investigated studying a simple nonlinear algebraic equation, whose coefficients are evaluated solving linear elastic problems. A numerical application is developed to determine the overall behavior of FRC, and to assess the proposed numerical procedure.

KEYWORDS: Fiber-Reinforced Concrete, Micromechanics, Fracture Mechanics, Numerical Procedure.

FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE

Cementitious materials, such as concrete and mortar, are characterized by brittle behavior, with development of cracks also for low values of positive deformations; hence, the tensile strength of such materials is very low. The addition of short steel fibers in the concrete material allows to increase the tensile strength, reducing the cracking development, and to improve the ductility, the fatigue resistance and the energy absorption capability. In fact, for a tensile stress state, the fibers offer resistance to the crack opening, since they behave as stiff bridges between the two fracture edges.

Experimental evidences show that the behavior of short fibre reinforced concrete FRC depends upon several factors: the amount, the geometry and the distribution of the fibers in the concrete and the adhesion fiber-concrete.

Under unidirectional tensile loading, the FRC constitutive law is characterized by three different stress-strain responses [1, 2, 3]:

- linear elastic response until the tensile strength of the matrix is reached when microcracks start to develop;
- strain hardening behavior due to the bridging forces imposed by fibres which are proportional to the crack opening displacement;
- strain softening response, after the maximum tensile strength of the composite is reached, due to debonding of fibres from the concrete and the coalescence and growing of microcracks.

MICROMECHANICS OF FRC COMPOSITE

The fibre reinforced concrete is a composite material obtained by embedding short fibers in a matrix of concrete. Hence, the mechanical response of the FRC can be determined by applying the homogenization technique [4, 5, 6]. In fact, the stress-strain law can be determined as the relation between the average stress and the average strain in a representative volume element (RVE). Although the geometric arrangement of the fibers in the FRC composite is not regular, in this work to obtain a simple but at the same time effective model for a one-dimensional stress state, e.g. simple traction, only the fibers in the stress direction are considered. Furthermore, it can be assumed that statistically the fibers in the same direction are equally spaced one-to-another; this implies that the FRC composite material under unidirectional tensile loading is considered as regular, i.e. periodic. Moreover, a presence of a periodic distribution of microcracks is assumed.

In the following, a two-dimensional analysis of the fiber reinforced concrete is performed. This represents a further simplification in the modeling of the FRC, which is often adopted in computations.

Finally, the behavior of the FRC is studied considering a two-dimensional infinite elastic solid containing a doubly periodic array of stitching fibers and cracks of equal length subjected to extension in the direction orthogonal to the cracks [7]. The microcracks are geometrically characterized by initial length $2a_0$ which can grow during the increasing of the applied tension. Since it is required the determination of the overall response of the composite in the fibre-direction, i.e. along the x_2 -direction, the analysis can be performed considering only the unit cell V_u with dimensions a_1 and a_2 , reported in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: A quarter of repetitive cell considered for the analysis

To model the concrete cohesive behavior during the crack propagation, a process zone with length l is introduced at the crack tip. For a fixed value of the crack size a and of the process zone length l , the homogenization technique is applied considering the concrete as a linear elastic material, and the stitches characterized by a nonlinear response, because of the possible debonding of fibres from the concrete. The nonlinear homogenization procedure is split in two problems. The first one considers the homogenization problem of the linear elastic concrete material with cracks, the second one investigates on the effects of the fiber stitches.

Cohesive model through a damage interface approach

To simulate the crack propagation, a cohesive model is developed introducing an interface at the crack tip. The process zone is characterized by a linear softening behavior, so that the tensile normal stress σ is defined as linear decreasing function of the relative displacement Δv between the two sides of the interface. In Fig. 2 the tensile strength of the material is denoted by f_t and the area under the stress-displacement function is the fracture energy G_c .

Fig. 2: Constitutive law of the matrix-matrix interface

The interface model introduced has the classical mechanical interpretation of distributed springs in the x_1 - and x_2 - directions and it is characterized by the following constitutive law:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tau \\ \sigma \end{bmatrix} = (1-D) \begin{bmatrix} K_\tau^{\text{int}} & 0 \\ 0 & K_\sigma^{\text{int}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta u \\ \Delta v \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where K_τ^{int} and K_σ^{int} are the stiffnesses of the distributed springs in the x_1 - and x_2 - directions, Δu , Δv are the x_1 - and x_2 - components of the relative displacements of opposite points on the crack edges, τ and σ are the shear and normal interface stresses, and D is the damage variable ($0 \leq D \leq 1$).

The analysis starts considering a process zone increasing its length l from zero to a final value L . When the process zone has reached its maximum length L , the crack starts to develop. The process zone length is kept constant during the crack opening.

It is assumed that the distribution of relative displacements Δv along the process zone has a cubic profile, thus it results:

$$\Delta v = -\frac{2\xi^3}{L^3}(\Delta v_c - \Delta v_0) + \frac{3\xi^2}{L^2}(\Delta v_c - \Delta v_0) + \Delta v_0 \quad (2)$$

where the abscissa ξ has its origin at the beginning of the process zone, i.e. at opposite side of the crack tip. The relationship between the damage D and the relative displacements Δv is given by:

$$D = \frac{\Delta v_c (\Delta v - \Delta v_0)}{\Delta v (\Delta v_c - \Delta v_0)} \quad (3)$$

so that it results $D=1$ and $\Delta v=\Delta v_c$, at the crack tip ($\xi=L$), $D=0$ and $\Delta v=\Delta v_0$ and at the beginning of the process zone ($\xi=0$). The constitutive equation of the interface along the process zone is evaluated combining (3) with equation (1) and (2).

Stitch model for fibers

In order to take into account the pull-out of the bridging fibers from the concrete matrix, an elasto-plastic constitutive law is considered for the fibers [8, 9]. In fact, it is assumed that the bridging forces are linear elastic, i.e. they are proportional to the crack opening displacements until a critical value is reached. Then, fibres debond from the matrix and the bridging closure forces suddenly drop to a lower value due to frictional pull-out. In Fig. 3, the bridging force-displacement relation is schematically reported.

Fig. 3: Force displacement response of the fiber

Hence, a special constitutive law is considered to model the bridging action of n_s fibres. Each bridging fiber connects two points lying on the opposite edge of a crack. The relative displacement Δv_i in the x_2 -direction between the two opposite points of the crack, corresponding to the i -th fiber, and the stitch force F_i orthogonal to the crack is given by the following relations:

$$F_i = K^f \Delta v_i \quad \text{if} \quad \Delta v_i < \Delta v_m \quad (4)$$

$$F_i = F_c \quad \text{if} \quad \Delta v_i \geq \Delta v_m \quad (5)$$

where K^f is the stiffness of the stitch fiber, F_c is the residual bridging force due to friction and F_m is the maximum force of the fiber, corresponding to the limit relative displacement Δv_m in the direction orthogonal to the crack (see Fig. 3).

FRC RESPONSE

Homogenization of cracked concrete

The estimate of the overall stiffness of the cracked concrete, in x_2 -direction, is derived from the solution of the elastostatic problems of the unit cell V_u subjected to a mean strain state ε^o_{22} . The classical field governing equations of the elastostatic problem are completed with the following boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1(0, x_2) &= 0 & \sigma_{12}(0, x_2) &= 0 & \forall x_2 \in [0, a_2] \\
 u_1(a_1, x_2) &= 0 & \sigma_{12}(a_1, x_2) &= 0 & \forall x_2 \in [0, a_2] \\
 \\
 u_2(x_1, 0) &= 0 & \sigma_{12}(x_1, 0) &= 0 & \forall x_1 \in [0, a_1] \\
 & & \sigma_{12}(x_1, 0) = \sigma_{22}(x_1, 0) &= 0 & \forall x_1 \in [0, a_1] \\
 u_2(x_1, a_2) &= \delta & \sigma_{12}(x_1, a_2) &= 0 & \forall x_1 \in [0, a_1]
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\delta = \varepsilon^o_{22} a_2$. Then, the mean stress in the x_2 -direction is computed as:

$$\sigma^o_{22} = \frac{1}{V_u} \int_{V_u} \sigma_{22}(x_1, x_2) dV = \frac{a_2}{V_u} \int_0^{a_1} \sigma_{22}(x_1, a_2) dx_1 \tag{7}$$

Finally, the overall elastic modulus E in x_2 -direction can be recovered, such that $E = \sigma^o_{22} / \varepsilon^o_{22}$. The resultant reactive stress $R^{(\delta)}$, is defined as:

$$R^{(\delta)} = \int_0^{a_1} \sigma_{22}(x_1, a_2) dx_1 \tag{8}$$

thus, the equation (7) gives:

$$R^{(\delta)} = a_1 \sigma^o_{22} = a_1 E \varepsilon^o_{22} = \frac{a_1 E}{a_2} \delta = K \delta \tag{9}$$

where $K = a_1 E / a_2$ is the overall stiffness of the unit cell.

Then, it is possible to determine the displacements of the points lying on the crack edge, where the stitching forces are applied. The relative displacement $\Delta v_i^{(\delta)}$ in the x_2 -direction, of the point corresponding to the position of the i -th fiber, is proportional to δ , and can be written as:

$$\Delta v_i^{(\delta)} = \mu_i \delta \tag{10}$$

where μ_i is an influence coefficient.

Effects of the stitch fibers on the unit cell

The unit cell is subjected to n_s forces F_i due to the presence of the n_s stitching fibers. The analysis is performed considering n_s different structural schemes, each characterized by the presence of only one force. Thus, the i -th elastostatic problem is governed by the field

equations and boundary conditions (6), with ε_{22}^o and completed with the application of the force F_i . The solution gives the resultant reactive stress $R^{(F_i)}$ evaluated at $x_2=a_2$, and the displacement $\Delta v_j^{(F_i)}$ of the point corresponding to the position of the j -th stitch:

$$\Delta v_j^{(F_i)} = \Lambda_{ji} F_i \quad R^{(F_i)} = \lambda_i F_i \quad (11)$$

where λ_i is an influence coefficient and Λ_{ji} is a compliance parameter.

Note that among all the n_s stitches, n_e fibers behave elastically, i.e. according to equation (4) $F_i = K^f \Delta v_i$ with $i = 1..n_e$, while the remaining $n_s - n_e$ fibers carry constant forces, i.e. because of (5) $F_i = F_c$ with $i = n_e + 1..n_s$.

FRC overall behavior

The FRC overall response is derived. Taking into account the relations (10, 11, 4, 5), the displacement of the i -th point is given by:

$$\Delta v_i = \Delta v_i^{(\delta)} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_s} \Delta v_i^{(F_j)} = \mu_i \delta + K^f \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} \Lambda_{ij} \Delta v_j + F_c \sum_{j=1+n_e}^{n_s} \Lambda_{ij} \quad (12)$$

Note that n_s equations (12) can be written. Denoting by I_{ij} the component of the unit matrix $n_e \times n_e$, the first n_e relations of the (12) can be rewritten in matricial form as:

$$\left(\mathbf{I} - K^f \mathbf{\Lambda} \right) \mathbf{V} = \boldsymbol{\mu} \delta + \boldsymbol{\alpha} F_c \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{V} is the vector of the displacements Δv_i and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the vector with components $\alpha_i = \sum_{j=1+n_e}^{n_s} \Lambda_{ij}$. Hence, solving the algebraic system (13) the vector \mathbf{V} can be recovered as:

$$\mathbf{V} = \left(\mathbf{I} - K^f \mathbf{\Lambda} \right)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu} \delta + \left(\mathbf{I} - K^f \mathbf{\Lambda} \right)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\alpha} F_c = \mathbf{P} \delta + \mathbf{S} F_c \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbf{P} = \left(\mathbf{I} - K^f \mathbf{\Lambda} \right)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}$ and $\mathbf{S} = \left(\mathbf{I} - K^f \mathbf{\Lambda} \right)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\alpha}$.

Then, the values of the n_e displacements given by (14) can be introduced into the remaining $n_s - n_e$ equations (12) to evaluate the displacements of the points subjected to the constant forces F_c :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta v_i &= \left[\mu_i + K^f \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} \Lambda_{ij} P_j \right] \delta + \left[K^f \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} \Lambda_{ij} S_j + \sum_{j=1+n_e}^{n_s} \Lambda_{ij} \right] F_c \\ &= \hat{P}_i \delta + \hat{S}_i F_c \quad \text{for } i = n_e + 1..n_s \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

with clear meaning of the symbols.

Taking into account the (9, 11, 14), the total stress reaction:

$$\begin{aligned}
R &= R^{(\delta)} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} R^{(F_i)} = R^{(\delta)} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} \lambda_i F_i \\
&= \left[K + K^f \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \lambda_i P_i \right] \delta + \left[K^f \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \lambda_i S_i + \sum_{i=1+n_e}^{n_s} \lambda_i \right] F_c \\
&= \bar{K} \delta + \bar{\lambda} F_c
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

CRACK EVOLUTION

The overall behavior of the FRC composite material is characterized initially by a linear elastic response then, after that the maximum tensile strength of the composite is reached, a strain softening response occurs because of the growing of cracks size and of the reduction of bridging forces. The computation of the FRC response is determined by adopting the homogenization technique described in the previous Section.

According to fracture mechanics the process zone evolution and the crack propagation take place when the potential energy rate reaches a critical value, characteristic of the matrix material. Let the unit cell V_u reported in Fig. 1 be considered. The potential energy at solution, for a given value of the process zone l and the crack size a , is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} &= -\frac{1}{2} R \delta - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} F_i \Delta v_i \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} R \delta - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} F_i \Delta v_i - \frac{1}{2} F_c \sum_{i=n_e+1}^{n_s} \Delta v_i
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Because of the equations (15, 16), the potential energy (17) takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} &= -\frac{1}{2} (\bar{K} \delta + \bar{\lambda} F_c) \delta - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} [F_i (P_i \delta + S_i F_c)] - \frac{1}{2} F_c \sum_{i=n_e+1}^{n_s} (\hat{P}_i \delta + \hat{S}_i F_c) \\
&= -[A \delta^2 + B \delta F_c + C (F_c)^2]
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where it is set:

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= \bar{K} + K^f \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} (P_i)^2 \\
B &= \bar{\lambda} + 2K^f \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} (P_i S_i) + \sum_{i=n_e+1}^{n_s} \hat{P}_i \\
C &= K^f \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} (S_i)^2 + \sum_{i=n_e+1}^{n_s} \hat{S}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The coefficients A , B and C of the quadratic equation (18), defining the potential energy at solution, depend upon the process zone length l and the crack size a .

The energy rate is computed differentiating the potential energy E defined in (18) with respect to l when $l < L$ then $dl > 0$ and $da = 0$, with respect to a when $l = L$ then $dl = 0$ and $da > 0$. Thus, the potential energy rate results:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial E}{\partial l} & \text{when } l < L \\ \frac{\partial E}{\partial a} & \text{when } l = L \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

There is evolution of the fracture when the energy rate reaches a critical value G_1 which depends on the process zone length l , on the maximum process zone length L , on the width a_1 of the cell and finally on the critical fracture energy of the concrete material G_c . In particular, G_1 results to be an increasing function of l , and it reaches its maximum value G_c when $l = L$ when $L \leq a_1$.

Finally, the evolution conditions for the process zone and the crack size are:

$$\left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial a} \delta^2 + \frac{\partial B}{\partial a} \delta F_c + \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} (F_c)^2 \right) = -2G_1 \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) is solved with respect to δ for each value of the process zone length l or of the crack size a . Once δ is computed, the relation (16) gives the total stress reaction. Thus, the overall stress-strain response is determined.

Note that the cohesive model CM tends to LEFM when the length of the process zone L tends to zero. The response of the cell through LEFM is obtained solving only equation (21) with $G_1 = G_c$.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In the numerical analyses, the following geometric and material data are considered:

$$\begin{array}{ll} a_1 & = 120 \text{ mm} \\ E_c & = 30000 \text{ N/mm}^2 \\ G_c & = 0.025 \text{ N/mm} \\ K_{\delta}^{int} & = 10^7 \text{ N/mm}^3 \\ K^f & = 2000 \text{ N/mm} \\ F_c & = 20 \text{ N} \\ L & = 200 \text{ mm} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{ll} a_2 & = 87 \text{ mm} \\ \nu_c & = 0.2 \\ f_t & = 3.0 \text{ N/mm}^2 \\ K_{\sigma}^{int} & = 10^7 \text{ N/mm}^3 \\ n_s & = 5 \\ F_m & = 20 \text{ N} \end{array}$$

where E_c and ν_c are the concrete Young modulus and the Poisson ratio, respectively.

According to the procedure discussed in the previous Section, the process zone and the crack development are governed by the potential energy rate. To compute this quantity, the coefficients A , B and C defined by relations (19) are evaluated numerically via Finite Element Method, using the code FEAP [10], for different values of the process zone length l and of the crack size a . Then, the derivative of the coefficients A , B and C are computed as finite differences. Thus, the numerical solution of the displacement δ is determined by solving the nonlinear equation (21). This equation allow to compute two solutions, but one of the two is not considered since it corresponds to $\delta < 0$.

Two different analyses of the unit cell are performed: unreinforced concrete through CM and fiber reinforced concrete through CM.

Fig 4: Total reaction versus applied displacement

In Fig. 4 the total reaction R versus the imposed displacement δ is plotted for plain concrete and for FRC. Furthermore in that figure the total bridging action of the fibers is plotted versus δ .

From the results of the analyses the following considerations can be drawn:

- there is little difference between the peak load of the plain concrete and of the FRC,
- the fibers bridging action becomes significant only after the peak load,
- the response of the FRC is irregular because of the concentrate bridging action of the fibers,
- although the irregular response, the FRC is characterized by a higher value of the fracture toughness compared to the unreinforced material,
- the total reaction R tends to the fibers total bridging action, when the concrete is completely cracked.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed approach, based on a homogenization technique, allows to evaluate the overall response of the fiber reinforced concrete under uniaxial tension through simple numerical computations. In particular, the developed numerical method allows to evaluate the nonlinear response of the material studying a second-order algebraic equation, whose coefficients are computed solving linear elastic problems. The procedure appears to be simple and computationally efficient; in fact, it permits to derive the softening behavior of the FRC, by solving a nonlinear algebraic equation instead of a nonlinear system of equations. Thus, the necessary iterations are performed on a single equation.

The numerical results of the analyses emphasize that the post-peak response of the reinforced material is improved due to the presence of the fibers. As the irregular response of the material is a consequence of the local bridging action of the fibers, some attempts should be

made in order to reduce this local effect of the fibers and to diffuse the bridging action of the fibers.

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